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PERCEIVE

Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections
through AI and Virtual Experiences

D8.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy and Plan

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2	FORTH	IDRYMA TECHNOLOGIAS KAI EREVNAS	Greece
3	ANAMNESIA	ANAMNESIA	France
3.1	IMKI	IMKI	France
4	NTNU	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	Norway
5	FRAUNHOFER	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV	Germany
6	MIC-MANN	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA MANN MUSEUM (MIC-MANN)	Italy
7	OSL-MUNCH	OSLO KOMMUNE MUNCH MUSEUM (OSL-MUNCH)	Norway
8	AIC	THE ART INSTITUTE OF CHICAGO US	USA
9	HOVERLAY	Hoverlay US	USA
10	HSLU	FACHHOCHSCHULE ZENTRALSCHWEIZ -HOCHSCHULE LUZERN CH	Switzerland
11	V&A	VICTORIA AND ALBERT MUSEUM UK	UK

Executive summary

PERCEIVE aims at creating a new way to preserve, perceive, curate, exhibit, understand and access colored Cultural Heritage collections and Digital Artworks. Therefore, promoting their re-appropriation. These collections are a priority because of their high fragility -requiring shared methods to preserve and exhibit them; the complexity of their study; the significance of their proper communication to future generations. PERCEIVE will support the shaping of a European common identity around the concepts of “care” and “diversity” and strengthen the digital market for the creative industries.

This Deliverable D8.1.b “Communication and Dissemination Strategy and Plan” is the updated version of D8.1.a, and it is outlining the overall project dissemination and communication strategy and associated actions, with the aim to define how and when dissemination will be achieved. The goal of the document is to ensure a well-balanced communication towards the target audiences, the media and the public to achieve Perceive project objectives.

Dissemination and communication are cross-cutting activities; therefore, the work is carried out in close cooperation with all the project WPs, to receive feedback and contents to be elaborated and used to disseminate and communicate the project externally and publicly. Each project partner has a task and/or efforts to be actively involved in disseminating and communicating the project results using the provided tools and following the defined strategies.

The Communication Strategy and Plan starts with general information about the communication objectives and strategy as well as internal and external communication. The Perceive strategy covers the key audiences, which are European Citizens/Society, the end users (Professionals and Educators), the scientific community and the financial actors.

The central source for information is the Perceive website (<http://perceive-horizon.eu/>) for the general public and the SharePoint Intranet for consortium members. Communication tools include also social media accounts (Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter YouTube), brochures, presentations, lectures of students and academics, a promo video of the project, webinars, websites and social media of project partners. The content will be presented in telegram channel Perceive, publications, press-releases and external and self-organised events. The deliverable also gives advice to partners on how to use the main social media channels. Finally, the document also presents an overview of events in which the project members will be represented. Project members have identified a clear set of key performance indicators to evaluate the performance of the communication activities.

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Document History

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1. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

PERCEIVE Communication and Dissemination Strategy is defined to promote the project during its entire development with the main goal of informing about activities and results, reaching out to society and explaining the benefits for the citizens. Publishing and disseminating the results of the project and attracting the major stakeholders to events and activities organized by the partnership, we intend to guarantee maximum impact of the project itself during its lifetime.

1.1 Target audience

PERCEIVE has identified the following target groups for its communication strategy:

[TG1]: European Citizens/Society (public at large),

[TG2]: end users - professionals in the field of CH and museums,

[TG3]: end users - Educators (especially high education),

[TG4]: end users - Professionals of the Creative Industries (including exhibition and light designers, game designers, Interactive Media designers, artists),

[TG5]: scientific community (i.e., in the field of conservation science, computer graphics, HCI, art history and archaeology, etc.),

[TG6]: financial actors (decision makers),

[TG7] financial actors (investors)

1.2 Objectives

The communication and dissemination strategy has defined specific objectives and main messages to be communicated to the audience:

[O1] Reaching the scientific and museum communities globally.

[O2] Explaining in simple and practical ways (for non-technical) the project results and outcomes, including the scientific approach, unveiling Artificial Intelligence.

[O3] Reaching the creative industries professionals in Europe.

[O4] Involving citizens, making them curious about the project, widening access.

[O5] Make aware decision makers and investors of the importance of proper economic support for activities that are not immediately profitable such as restoration and activities such as preservation.

[O6] Widening the communication about projects results and outcome to higher education (i.e., university courses of design etc.

The project follows the **SMART** approach for effective communication objectives:

- **Specific:** it contributes to the relevant change at the specific objective level
- **Measurable:** it is possible to measure the baseline, the target and, if necessary, the milestones
- **Achievable:** it is possible to achieve the target
- **Relevant:** it contributes to the change at a priority axis and Program level
- **Time-bound:** it is available and updated at different points in time

1.3 Communication Messages

In the following paragraph we report main communication messages and their reference audience.

TG1	<i>“Perceive Colors in artworks and looks for new experiences and engaging content” “Test the Prototypes” “What You PERCEIVE Is What You Get” (Paraphrasing the WYSIWYG).</i>
TG1	<i>“Travel back in time and PERCEIVE color aesthetic and cultural values in context, unveiling the original appearance of the past”.</i>
TG1	<i>“What makes you care? Re-appropriate colored artworks”.</i>
TG6, TG7	<i>“Invest in monitoring, conservation and restoration activities”.</i>
TG2	<i>“Develop new approaches to restoring objects without invasive treatments”.</i>
TG2	<i>“Improve understanding of colored collections, conserving and reconstructing them in a way that is safe for the objects”.</i>
TG2,4,5	<i>“Develop your understanding around colored artworks and AI”.</i>
TG2	<i>“Widen your audience and engage it in new ways, communicating the power of colors”.</i>
TG3	<i>“Improve your teaching on colored artworks and on their original appearance and how they were perceived, engage students improving dialogue with them”.</i>
TG2,4	<i>“Prevent colour alteration or damage of colored artworks in exhibitions” “prevent / predict colour change under specific lighting conditions”.</i>
TG4	<i>“Build your scientific credibility to the cultural heritage clients, strengthening your competitiveness when creating digital exhibitions, virtual worlds, serious games, immersive experiences based on scientifically evidenced knowledge”.</i>
TG2,3	<i>“Artificial Intelligence for Colored Collections out of the “black box”.</i>
TG2,4	<i>“Sell authenticity based PERCEIVE Experiences to set up your new business model”</i>
TG2,3,4	<i>“Design new PERCEIVE experiences and evaluate them with the Design ToolBox”.</i>
TG4	<i>“Speed up your workflow, develop variance, and be more competitive”.</i>
TG2,4,5	<i>“Learn how to use the services and tools”.</i>
TG5	<i>“Learn material modelling to PERCEIVE the materiality of color”.</i>
TG2,5	<i>“Test PERCEIVE infrastructure with your collection and datasets”.</i>
TG1,4	<i>“What do you perceive? What do they perceive?”.</i>
TG1,2,3,5	<i>“Open the Museum of colored collections, participate and co-create taking inspiration from the past, Sway opinion and Create Change”.</i>

2.1 Communication and Dissemination strategy during the project lifetime

This document is elaborated in order to generate an effective communication strategy aimed at the widespread dissemination of PERCEIVE objectives, activities and results between partners and audience involved in the project implementation using different communication channels. This paragraph describes how PERCEIVE will develop its strategy during the project's lifetime.

Year one (February 2023 – January 2024)

The first year of the project was devoted to the analysis of the needs and requirements, in line with the five scenarios of the project:

1. Lost Polychromy in classical Sculpture;
2. Color deterioration in Paintings;
3. Color deterioration in Textiles;
4. Color deterioration in Historical Photos (autochromes, etc.);
5. Colors in Digital Art.

The communication and dissemination strategy were dedicated therefore to those aspects and to partners' expertise presentation.

Specifically, the strategy included:

Partners' presentation	Short video interviews, articles and posts etc.	TG1, TG2
Scenarios' presentation	Interviews, videos about acquisitions, articles, posts	TG1, TG2, TG5
User needs	Interviews, articles and posts about the results from questionnaire	TG2, TG5
Technology	General State of the Art about AI and Image Based Rendering, Conservation Science analysis	TG3, TG4, TG5
Project presentation	Participation to events and conferences, Press releases from the Kick-Off Meeting event in Naples, Stories, Project Promo Trailer	TG1, TG2

Year two (February 2024 – January 2025)

The second year of the project is devoted to data acquisition and modelling and to the design of PERCEIVE technologies, therefore the strategy is dedicated to the identified tech components aligned with the Scenarios:

Specifically, the strategy includes:

User needs and Requirements	Presentation of results	TG2, TG5
Digital Assets of the Scenarios	Presentation of results	TG1, TG2
Technology	Data Acquisition and modelling, AI and Image Based Rendering technologies suited for the PERCEIVE scenarios; posts in socials and papers on designing tools and services, prototype design; presentation during the Midway Workshop foreseen at M15	TG3, TG4, TG5
Project presentation	Participation to events and conferences, Stories, Posts about project activities and applications	TG1, TG2, TG5

Year three (February 2025 – January 2026)

The third year of the project is devoted to the development and presentation of the PERCEIVE platform, Tools and Services, Prototypes and to the final hybrid exhibition.

Specifically, the strategy includes:

User needs and Requirements	Presentation of results	TG2, TG5
Digital Assets of the Scenarios	Presentation of results	TG1, TG2
Technology: prototypes	Presentation of the prototypes: posts in socials and papers, demonstrations in events and conferences, articles in specialised journals and magazines; you tube webinars and manuals; design toolkits	TG2, TG3, TG4, TG5, TG6, TG7
Technology: Tools and Services	Presentation of Tools and Services: posts in socials and papers, demonstrations in events and conferences, articles in specialised journals and magazines; YouTube webinars and manuals; Website implementation to include resources on tools and manuals for stakeholders.	TG2, TG3, TG4, TG5, TG6, TG7
Technology: Platform	Publication of resources in Web PERCEIVE portal, posts in socials and papers, demonstrations in events and conferences, articles in specialised journals and magazines; webinars; polychromy roundtable	TG2, TG3, TG4, TG5, TG6, TG7
Hybrid final event	Posts in socials and papers, press release, Articles, Video presentation	TG1, TG2, TG3, TG4, TG5, TG6, TG7

1.5 Plan and Activities

The following measures and activities have been identified.

Target	Obj.	Message	Measures and Activities Channels	Time Period
TG1	O4	M1, M10, M12, M19, M20	<p>Live streaming events and Videos on YouTube, Instagram, Facebook;</p> <p>Testing events of the prototypes, organised physically at museums or in International fairs and exhibitions (as VideoGameLab, Archeovirtual, Museum Next etc.); Focus groups on perception, caring and authenticity; Special events at the museums and outside museums / Final PERCEIVE demonstrator with online experiences, physical exhibit at the museums and open air museum, Catalogue and Publicity;</p> <p>Social media and national / cultural press (i. e. V&A will develop a specific social media and cultural press campaign to promote the project</p>	During (from M1) and After

			and its results); Website with videos and examples of the prototypes applied to case studies. Perceive Trailer. Access to Open Museum prototype	
TG2	O1, O2, O3	M3, M4, M5, M6, M8, M11, M13, M14, M16, M20	Hands-on Workshops with experts, Know-How Training Sessions on line (also in streaming on media channels such as Facebook or YouTube) and at museums on tools and services and prototypes (i.e. on light exposure and damage estimator that take into account the responsivity of the light-sensitive materials (as pigments/colorants) to the spectral power distribution features of a selected light source or that define safe limits of light exposure to achieve a balance between minimum risk and optimum rendering/display for a specific object and a selected type/unit of lighting source); Presentation at scientific events (i.e. MuseumNext...) Call for Datasets to involve and extend participation to other museums and institution; PERCEIVE Portal	During and After
TG3	O2, O6	M7, M11, M14	Training activities, prototypes and tools will improve the dialogue on the appearance of original colors, the tools produce proposals of interpretation to the scholar community that can be easily revised, based on new data and incorporating latest information and more importantly new interpretations based on open dialogue among experts.	During and After
TG4	O2, O3	M8, M9, M13, M14, M15, M16, M19, M20	Conference Participation to present project results: i.e. V&A participation to ICON, VARI conferences; Events participation of interest for SMEs with B2B sessions: i.e. Vivatech, GEN, SIA, SITEM, Siggraph, Laval Virtual, Videogamelab (Anamnesia plans to attend 10 in France but also internationally); Online Workshops (i.e. V&A organisation of Workshops to communicate and disseminate results); Testing tools and services sessions; Testing prototypes sessions; Know-How training activities and online tutorials for Creative Industry professionals dedicated to the use of the API, of the tools and services and of the prototypes and related blueprints; Exhibition/light design live sessions and demonstration in museums with the support of dedicated tools; Co-creation sessions with Perceive Design Toolkit	During and After
TG5	O1, O2	M5, M16, M17, M18	Know-How training sessions for the scientific community (bridging with E-RIHS, IPERION HS training activities under <u>HS Academy</u> thus extending participation to the wider heritage science community); Open Access Publications on scientific journals: 2 publications by V&A on MDPI journals, V&A conservation journal, V&A magazine, ICON website, V&A website; by FORTH and CNR on <u>Heritage Science</u> , <u>Heritage</u> , sections <u>Digital Heritage</u> and <u>Museum and Heritage</u> and <u>Material and Heritage</u> ; by CNR on <u>DAACH</u> , <u>ACM JOCCH</u> , <u>Journal of Cultural Heritage</u> , <u>JOURNAL OF COMPUTER-MEDIATED COMMUNICATION</u> , <u>IEEE MULTIMEDIA</u> , <u>Multimodal User Interfaces</u> , <u>HUMAN-COMPUTER INTERACTION</u> , <u>International Journal of HERITAGE STUDIES</u> ; Presentation at Scientific Conferences: EUROGRAPHICS Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage, DigitalHeritage, <u>International Round Table on Polychromy</u> in	After M18 or later

			Ancient Sculpture and Architecture, “Polychromy Round Table” dedicated to the study of the polychromy of ancient sculpture and architecture; Standardisation activities during workshops; Open Access Books on the theory (“ <i>Chromatic Visions: Exploring Colour in Art, Archaeology and Digital Realities</i> ” - provisory title) and technologies (title to be defined); Press release and communication through magazines, tv specials. Organisation of conference within the Color and Visual Computing Symposium (CVCS) in 2023, hosted by NTNU.	
TG6 and TG7	O5	M2, M20	Press Conference (with demonstrating activities); Press release; Participation to high level events at the Ministries; Online Workshops participated by decision makers; Tech Events - Vivatech	During

1.6 Key Performance Indicators of the Communication and Dissemination strategy

The project will include and verify, within the activities of WP1 and specifically Task 1.4, the following KPI indicators for the Communication and Dissemination, in line with the planned measures and activities.

COMMUNICATION	
Media Coverage Targets	40
Social Media Targets	1500
Website Targets	1000
Event-related target (including participants and media coverage)	200
Video production targets (views and shares)	500
Communication Material Uses (leaflets, posters, flyers)	20
DISSEMINATION	
Peer-reviewed scientific publication targets (number and type of articles)	Min 5
Scientific conference presentation and publication targets (number and type)	Min 6
Policy Brief targets (number and profile of participants at events)	Min. 50

Some preliminary results of the work carried out during the first year (2023) of the project have been summarized in the following paragraphs, while insights on the communication strategy can specifically be found in paragraph [3.7 Social Media Channels and plan](#).

2. Dissemination Plan

2.1 Press Campaign

Press release and communication through magazines and TV specials will be prepared during the project lifetime, in the occasion of main events or presentation of results.

A Press Release has been prepared for the Kick-Off Meeting at the MANN Museum in Naples, in Italian and English, and it is accessible through different channels, including the project website and CNR Press Office website (<https://www.cnr.it/it/nota-stampa/e-18439/presentazione-del-progetto-perceive>).

Articles and News have been prepared by magazines, journals and online portals, including:

- the official Italian ANSA (https://www.ansa.it/campania/notizie/2023/03/03/il-mann-a-colori-al-via-progetto-europeo-perceive_510613d4-6a09-4d31-94a6-423708f2ad01.html)
- AGENZIA CULT: <https://www.agenziacult.it/cultura-e-digitale/cultura-e-digitale-lunedì-al-mann-lancio-del-progetto-europeo-perceive/>
- ART TRIBUNE: <https://www.tribune.com/mostre-evento-arte/perceive/>
- IL MATTINO
https://www.ilmattino.it/napoli/cultura/mann_napoli_progetto_perceive_ai_intelligenza_artificiale-7265403.html

2.2 Scientific Conferences and Events

The following paragraph presents main scientific conference and events of high relevance for the PERCEIVE project. During those conferences and events, partners will organise sessions and present their work.

PERCEIVE partners will attend the conferences and organise sessions or participation in line with the projects work program.

2023: During the first year most of the involvement regarded the presentation of the project, of the state of the art in the different domains and of needs and requirements results, and have been summarized as follows:

- **Color and Visual Computing Symposium (CVCS):** <https://www.cvcs.no/>
A platform for fruitful discussions and exploration of recent theoretical advances and emerging practical applications of colour and visual information processing
 - **NTNU Conference (November 2023): NETApp Workshop on Material Appearance**
- **Co-organisation of EUROGRAPHICS Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage (September 2023):**
GCH aims to engage practitioners and researchers across the world working at the interface of novel digital technologies and cultural heritage.
- **BrownBag Presentation (HSLU)**

HSLU addresses pertinent issues surrounding CH in the field of digital arts through born digital artworks and along with the PERCEIVE project team at HSLU. Co-design a post-covid art space along with the N55 Arts Collective that appeals to a wide audience through the application of a concept of exploration based on engagement with the use physical space coupled with modern technologies such as AR, VR and MR, Projection Mapping, Interactive Narrative Holograms to bring hybrid online and on-site experiences which can present an assemblage of narratives and artworks stemming from diverse art museums.

- **Appamat/IS&T International workshop on material appearance:** [Appamat/IS&T International workshop on material appearance - GDR APPAMAT \(cnrs.fr\)](#)

In the framework of the *IS&T Color Imaging Conference (CIC 2023)* held in Paris 13-17 November, Appamat and IS&T collocate a workshop on material appearance, with a special session on cosmetics and facial appearance. PERCEIVE participated with two presentations:

- *Recovering lost polychromy: digital reconstruction of ancient Roman sculptures* – Yoko Arteaga, NTNU, Norway
Presentation on a novel methodology that aims to bridge the distance between scientists, museum professionals, and developers and allow them to combine their skills and knowledge, based on the acquisition of accurate material appearance data relying on real residues of the mostly lost polychromy.
- *The Scream (ca. 1910) through the Years: from Photographic Documentation to Digital Rejuvenation* – Irina Ciortan, NTNU, Norway

2024: During the second year most of the presentations will involve results in line with data modelling, AI and Computer Vision.

2025: During the third year the involvement of PERCEIVE partners will be more consistent and will include the presentation of project results, outcomes, prototypes, tools and services.

Among the conferences to which PERCEIVE will attend there are:

- **HCI conference:** <https://www.hci.international>
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HUMAN-COMPUTER INTERACTION
- **The 6th InART2024 Conference:** [InART2024 Conference - Museum of Cultural History \(uio.no\)](#) (Oslo, June 4-7, 2024)
Organized by the Museum of Cultural History of the University of Oslo, InART2024 aims to merge natural sciences and conservation, providing a dynamic space for active interaction, scientific exchange, and debates on the central issues of heritage science research. Contributors from diverse fields are welcome to join and create an interdisciplinary discussion about cultural heritage conservation within the fields of archaeological objects, artworks, built heritage, etc.
- **MuseumNext:** <https://www.museumnext.com/events/>
MuseumNext is a leading network for those working in museums.
- **Siggraph:** <https://www.siggraph.org/siggraph-events/conferences/>
The Premier Conference & Exhibition on Computer Graphics & Interactive Techniques
- **Polychromy Round Table:** <https://www.polychromyroundtable.com/more.php>
International Round Table on Polychromy in Ancient Sculpture and Architecture.

- **DigitalHeritage**

A federated event of the leading scientific meetings in information technology for heritage, the Congress will for the first time bring VSMM, Eurographics GCH, UNESCO's Memory of the World, Arqueologica2.0, Archaeovirtual, Digital Art Week and special events from CAA, CIPA, Space2Place, ICOMOS ICIP, and multiple others together in one venue with a prestigious joint publication. A ground-breaking public display of cutting-edge digital heritage projects

- Autumn 2025 (under preparation)
- Co-organisation and Perceive session

- **Co-Design Ideation Workshop**

In December 2023, a first iteration of design workshops was organized: the Co-Design Ideation Workshop consisted in a series of 2-hour ideation workshops in collaboration with some of the partners (MANN, HSLU, OSL-MUNCH, and CNR). The ideation workshop aimed at defining ideas and drafting design briefs for potential digital and hybrid experiences for visitors (prototypes) within the project, following the stakeholders' needs and requirements collected in the WP2 survey (as described in Deliverable 2.2). To guide the participants during the workshop a specific deck of cards was developed on the basis of the VisitorBox project available in the GIFT Box framework (<https://gifting.digital/visitorbox-design-cards/>). The results and in-depth analyses of the carried-out workshops have been described in Deliverable 6.1.

2.3 Public or Commercial Events

The following paragraph presents main public and commercial events of high relevance for the PERCEIVE project. During those events, partner will organise sessions and present their work and demos.

Among the events PERCEIVE will be attending over the next two years there are:

- **Archeovirtual:** <http://www.archeovirtual.it/index.php/en/home-2/>
ArcheoVirtual is the multimedia exhibition which is, since more than 12 years the flagship of the Borsa Mediterranea del Turismo Archeologico (BMTA). It is focussed on digital applications and projects of virtual archaeology, a field of research which aims to study, analyse and understand Cultural Heritage and its context through a process of acquisition of data, reconstruction, continuous check thanks to visualization and simulation techniques.
- **Laval Virtual:** <https://laval-virtual.com/>
Laval Virtual, the first event dedicated to immersive technologies (virtual reality, augmented reality) which gathers all European AR/VR community since 1999.
- **SITEM:** <https://www.sitem.fr/en/>
International trade show for museums, cultural venues and tourist sites: equipment, enhancement & innovation.
- **VideoGameLab:** <https://www.romevideogamelab.it/en/>
Rome Videogame Lab is the first and only Italian festival of the applied games, those interactive virtual simulations of reality which, throughout playing, achieve educational, marketing goals and social and cultural awareness. The event, which takes place in the

Cinecittà Studios, was born with the aim of raising awareness of the world of video games created not only to entertain, but mainly aimed at learning in various fields: healthcare, scientific dissemination, education, cultural heritage and more.

- **Vivatech:** <https://vivatechnology.com/>
VivaTech accelerates innovation by connecting startups, tech leaders, major corporations and investors responding to our world's biggest challenges.

Moreover, during the first year, PERCEIVE has already organised some events to reach the different target audience:

- **PERCEIVE Kick-Off at MANN (March 2023):** [Launch event – PERCEIVE \(perceive-horizon.eu\)](https://perceive-horizon.eu)

The Kick-Off meeting of the project was organised in March and hosted by one of PERCEIVE partners, the National Archaeological Museum of Naples (MANN). During the three days conference, open to scholar communities, cultural and creative sectors and civil society, it was given an overview of the structure of the project, the scenarios it would be dealing with, and the different working packages, its goals, and objectives, along with the presentation of each partner and their specific role. Moreover, on the last day of the event, only open to partners, an interactive “Rainbow Session” was also organised, as an additional moment to stimulate discussion and ideas among the members.

- **Expert Room at MANN (June 2023):** <https://journees-archeologie.eu/c-2023/lg-it/Italia/fiche-initiative/18353/Museo-Archeologico-Nazionale-di-Napoli/> / (organised in collaboration with MANN).

During the *European Archaeology Days 2023*, two public events were organised at the National Archaeologic Museum of Naples (MANN) concurrently to the CNR mission at the Museum to digitise and carry out an archaeometric campaign on some of the displayed statues that were chosen as case studies for PERCEIVE. During the events' days brief guided tours were provided with the aim of giving an overview of the whole facets and aspects of the research process of polychromy identification and recognition, explaining how much information can be acquired using different techniques and highlighting the whole workflow's obstacles and challenges. After the visits all participants were asked to fill in a very brief survey that contributed to acquiring precious information and insights on the visitors' needs and, on their curiosities and raised questions towards the specific topic of ancient polychromy. The exact configuration of the experiences and their results have been thoroughly described in Deliverable 2.2.

2.4 Training plan

The PERCEIVE training is dedicated to the involvement and knowledge acquisition of technological/design components of the project for Educators, Scientific Community, CH institutions and professionals and Creative Industries.

The strategy includes the preparation and launch of webinars, hands-on workshops and ready-to-use material accessible through the PERCEIVE portal (to be launched at the beginning of 2025).

The activities will be disseminated through the social channels (especially LinkedIn and Telegram) and organised in line with specialised conferences and events where the stakeholders could be reached (i.e., Museum conferences and demonstrations, B2B events etc.).

Articles in specialised magazines will be published.

As of the first-year, part of these training has already been carried out, in the form of two workshops dedicated to PERCEIVE partners:

Workshop on Caring, Authenticity and Curiosity

In June 2023 PERCEIVE performed a first workshop on Caring, Authenticity and Curiosity that included fifteen-minutes presentations by the different partners on their research on the topics:

- o Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC), Samuele Spotti (CNR ISPC) “Authenticity in XR applications”.
- o Janina Woods (HSLU) “Creating Care in Interactive and Immersive Media”.
- o Arthur Clay, HSLU “Prototyping of Caring”.
- o Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC), Gabriele Fiorenza (UNIBO) “Caring Attitude and Interactive Media”.
- o Sophia Sotiropoulou (FORTH) “Authenticity in the perception of the original (colour) appearance: ideas on Authenticity in XR applications”.
- o Manuele Veggi (UNIROMA) “Art practices to elicit care and engagement through Colours and Conservation Science data”.
- o Cristiana Barandoni (MANN) Federica Bonifazi (CNR ISPC) “Curiosity and Colors”.
- o Irina-Mihaela Ciortan (NTNU) “AI image-making tools: friend or foe?”.

2.5 Publications

The publication plan includes:

- **Open Access Books:** two books are set to be published:
 1. The first one “Chromatic Visions: Exploring Colour in Art, Archaeology and Digital Realities” (provisory title) is set to be published in June 2024 and will deal with PERCEIVE theoretic themes and aspects; More insights on this publication will be described in Deliverable 8.3.
 2. The second one (title to be defined) will instead be published at the end of the third year and will deal with all the technologic topics of the project, including the development of tools and prototypes.
- **Scientific Publications** will be prepared for journals, including:
 - o V&A conservation journal,
 - o V&A magazine,
 - o Elsevier DAACH,
 - o ACM JOCCH,
 - o Elsevier Journal of Cultural Heritage,
 - o JOURNAL OF COMPUTER-MEDIATED COMMUNICATION,
 - o IEEE MULTIMEDIA,
 - o Multimodal User Interfaces,

- HUMAN-COMPUTER INTERACTION,
- International Journal of HERITAGE STUDIES

As of January 2024, several publications have already been made available in various forms:

Articles on PERCEIVE website:

- Clay, A. (2023, September). Born Digital Art: Fleeting Masterpieces. <http://perceive-horizon.eu/index.php/2023/09/01/born-digital-art-fleeting-masterpieces/>
- Clay A., Grieco G., Fedon C., & Lanfranconi D. (2023, November). Adaptive Horizons: Navigating museums in a Post-Pandemic world. <http://perceive-horizon.eu/index.php/2023/11/09/adaptive-horizons-navigating-museums-in-a-post-pandemic-world/>

Journal:

- Martinez Pandiani D., & Pescarin S. (2022). “Beyond Static Colors: An Interactive Participatory Design Perspective on Color-Centric Experiences”. *International Journal of Conservation Science*. 13, SI1, 2022: 1691-1706 https://ijcs.ro/public/IJCS-22-125_Pandiani.pdf

Poster:

- Ciortan, I., Trumpy, G., Sandu, I., & Bjørngård, H. (2023). The Scream (ca. 1910) through the Years: from Photographic Documentation to Spatio-Temporal Modelling. The Eurographics Association. <https://diglib.eg.org/xmlui/handle/10.2312/gch20231182>

Pre-print:

- Pescarin S., Barandoni C., Bonanno V., Ciortan I., Clay A., Doherty B., Arteaga Y., Fiorenza G., Langford C., Magrini D., Monico L., Pandiani M., Sandu I., Trumpy G., Verri G., & Santos R. (2023). Perceiving Coloured Collections: the PERCEIVE theory. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8226551>
- Veggi, M., & Pescarin, S. (2023). Experimental Protocol on Creative Engagement and Meaning Creation in Interactive Experiences for Cultural Heritage. Tabular Data (v0.9 (preprint)) [dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8027736>
- Spotti S., & Pescarin S. (2023). Cultural Probe Kit on Authenticity triggers in XR experiences: activity book and diary for designers to explore and develop authentic experiences in Digital Heritage (0.9). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286449>
- Bonifazi F., & Pescarin S. (2023). Cultural Probe Kit on Curiosity triggers in XR experiences: activity book and diary for designers to explore and solicit curiosity in Digital Heritage (Versione 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286038>
- Pescarin S., Fiorenza G., & Veggi M. (2023). PERCEIVE Cultural Probe Kit on Caring attitude in XR experiences: activity book, diary and art practices for designers to explore and solicit care in Cultural Heritage domain (Versione 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8285611>

Proceedings:

- Olbrich, M., Zapf, A., Stiegemann, C., & Pröbe, A. (2023). Large Room Scale Augmented Reality in an Unaltered World Heritage Site. The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/GCH.20231172>
- Pöllabauer, T., Kühn, J., Li, J., & Kuijper, A. (2023). One-to-many Reconstruction of 3D Geometry of cultural Artifacts using a synthetically trained Generative Model. The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/GCH.20231161>
- Sinha, S. N., & Weinmann, M. (2023). Portrait2Bust: DualStyleGAN-based Portrait Image Stylization Based on Bust Sculpture Images. The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/GCH.20231159>
- Clay, A., Trumpy, G., Weinmann, M., & Wetzel, R. (2023). Prototyping Care: Two Case Studies. The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/GCH.20231178>
- Trumpy, G., & Gigilashvili, D. (2023). Using Spatial Augmented Reality to Increase Perceived Translucency of Real 3D Objects. The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/GCH.20231162>
- Pescarin, S., Città, G., Gentile, M., & Spotti, S. (2023). Authenticity in VR and XR Experiences: a Conceptual Framework for Digital Heritage. The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/GCH.20231153>
- Pescarin, S., Cerato, I., D'Annibale, E., Fanini, B., Ferdani, D., Manganelli Del Fà, R., Marasco, A., Massidda, M., Palombini, A., & Ronchi, D. (2023). Hybrid XR Collaborative and Guided Experiences in Cultural Heritage: Brancacci POV Prototype. The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/GCH.20231171>

2.6 Collaboration with other EU projects

With the support of the European Commission, the PERCEIVE project is part of the Digital Cultural Heritage Cluster network, that interconnect projects funded under the same Program. Specifically PERCEIVE is working towards the development of a common dissemination and communication plan, together with:

- **MuseIT:** The MuseIT Project started on October first, 2022. With the broader ambition of equality, democratisation and social inclusion, MuseIT proposes technologies that facilitate and widen access to cultural assets, and helps preserve and safeguard cultural heritage in an inclusive way, website: <https://www.muse-it.eu/>;
- **PREMIERE:** The overall objective of PREMIERE is to develop and validate a comprehensive ecosystem of digital applications, powered by leading edge AI, XR and 3D technologies, designed to fulfil the needs of diverse end-user communities involved in the main stages of the of the lifecycle of performing arts productions, including amateur and professional performers, performance art producers and curators, performance art spectators and scholars, website: <https://premiere-project.eu/the-project/>;
- **MEMORISE:** More and more victims of Nazi persecution and eyewitnesses of the Holocaust pass away. To keep their memories alive, it is therefore imperative to develop new strategies to tell their stories to younger generations. MEMORISE will make use of digital technology to digitize diaries of victims, testimonials, and other materials that inhere memories, and make

them accessible to the public in new forms. Our plans include the development of a novel smartphone app that narrates victims' experiences based on diaries, augmented reality (AR) solutions to enhance memorial site visitor experiences, and a web-based interface that gives access to all materials and supports narrative virtual experiences for everyone, website: <https://memorise.sdu.dk/about-memorise/>;

- **MEMENTOES:** The project pairs three museums focused on historical injustices – the USSR's gulags, wars impacting children, and a mining disaster – with independent game developers. Together, they'll develop games that allow users to inhabit the perspectives of different groups involved in these events, emphasizing the experiences of regular people. The consortium will also publish guidelines and best practices for partnerships between museums and game developers, so the MEMENTOES approach can be replicated in future projects, website: <https://memorise.sdu.dk/about-memorise/>;
- **SHIFT:** SHIFT is strategically conceived to deliver a set of loosely coupled, technological tools, that offers cultural heritage institutions the necessary impetus to stimulate growth, and embrace the latest innovations in artificial intelligence, machine learning, multi-modal data processing, digital content transformation methodologies, semantic representation, linguistic analysis of historical records, and the use of haptics interfaces to effectively and efficiently communicate new experiences to all citizens (including people with disabilities). Project presentation: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060660>.

As part of this strategy PERCEIVE also proposed a common participation of all the projects to Digital Heritage World Congress 2025, an event bridging among different cultural heritage domains and existing conferences and organised around the interconnection between digital and heritage themes.

2.7 DEMONSTRATOR: final event

At the end of the third year a final event will be set up: **PERCEIVE Hybrid Exhibition** will consist in three types of events:

1. A **scientific** event on colored collections and their study, reconstruction, conservation, and communication, during which the results and outcomes of the project will be presented, including the AI core, the tools and services, and the prototypes. This first event will target the scientific community, cultural heritage institutions, policy makers and creative industries.
1. A final **exhibition**, that will be organised in physical locations, with original or reproduced elements of collections and with digital applications complementing the visit. This second event will target citizens (and specifically schools, families, groups of friends), and experts in the domain. The digital applications will be what in PERCEIVE are named as "prototypes" and whose first ideas were developed during the Co-Design Workshop.
2. A **virtual exhibition**, that will be organised completely online as a collaborative immersive experience on coloured collections and their fragility. The target audience will this time be the European citizens.

The final event will also be accompanied by an extensive press campaign, with materials and flyers based on the project template and promoted on the project and partners' social media channels.

3. Communication Plan

3.1 Logo and Visual Identity

As for the visual and identity strategy, ANAMNESIA has developed a plan with several activities, some already carried out, others to be foreseen.

Figure 1: PERCEIVE logos

The first step was the creation of the PERCEIVE logo (both in colors and in black and white); more variants have been developed together with an icon, the PERCEIVE eye, to quickly represent and identify the project (Figure 1). Idea behind the logo and why we created it: Graphic interplay between the eye and the letter C highlights perception and the way we view artworks. This approach enables the creation of a logo that is used in its complete form integrated into text and then as a symbol. A color gradient identifies each research group, which together constitute the Perceive project. Simple, modern, and dynamic shapes create a timeless and legible visual identity for each participating country.

Additionally, to enhance the visuals of the website, various graphics have been arranged for the Homepage together with five specific icons for the five scenarios (Figure 1):

1. An ancient statue for the scenario of lost polychromy;
2. A paintbrush for the scenario on change of colors in paintings and works on paper;
3. A dress for the scenario on fading in textiles;
4. A camera for the scenario on fading in historic photos collections;
5. A digital paper for the scenario on born digital artworks.

Figure 2: PERCEIVE scenario logos

Moreover, graphics for the webinars, videos, posters, and flyers have been developed, whereas promo video trailer based on the storyboard available on the [Cordis](#) website are still in progress.

Figure 3: Example of PERCEIVE’s flyer.

Lastly, an image template is used for each institute: for instance in the following example, the partner logo photo occupies the background, while the white circles in the corner have been chosen as characteristic of PERCEIVE together with the typography.

Figure 4: Example of partner logo with PERCEIVE’s template.

3.2 Project flyer and brochure

The project flyer and the project presentation brochure are currently (January 2024) on progress and will be finalised before the end of March to be used for future events.

At the end of the third year, on the occasion of the final event, the same template of the project flyer will also be adopted for the design of “mini flyer” that will be produced to describe each of the realized prototypes.

Figure 5: Exemplar template for the Project Flyer.

3.3 Project roll up

The project roll up is also currently (January 2024) on progress and will be finalised before the end of March to be used for future events.

Figure 6: Exemplar template for the Project Roll Up.

3.4 Presentation template

Figure 7: Perceive INSTITUTION and KEYNOTE presentation template.

Figure 8: Perceive WG presentation template.

Figure 9: Perceive WP presentation template.

3.5 Project videos

During the PERCEIVE Kick-Off Meeting in March 2023 partners' interviews were realised and gathered in short videos that have already been posted on the projects' social media (Facebook and Instagram) and will be published on the YouTube channel as soon as it will be open in March.

The project presentation video is already in progress and is set to be published both on socials and YouTube at the start of March.

Videos presentation for each prototype will also be drafted and made available at the end of the project, and in meantime short videos of the work in progress activities and acquisition campaign for the different scenarios are being posted in the form of Instagram and Facebook stories to enhance followers' engagement.

Figure 10: Presentation videos template.

3.6 Website strategy

1st year website:

- Develop the website with five sections: Home, News, Project, Contact, Partners (**Figure 1**).
- Link to social medias created (Linkedin, Facebook, Instagram).
- Link to Zenodo for scientific papers.

Figure 11: Homepage of the PERCEIVE website.

- Presentation of the Horizon Europe project.

Figure 12: Project presentation PERCEIVE.

- Presentation and introduction of each partner and describe their expertise.

PERCEIVE Project Partners Scenarios News Results Related Platform

The PERCEIVE Consortium

The PERCEIVE Consortium involves 12 partners from Europe and beyond, including research centers and creative industries.

CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE

CNR is the main research institutions in Italy. It participates with its Institute of Heritage Science (ISPC) and Institute of Chemical Sciences and Technologies (SCITEC) and its labs.

CNR ISPC expertise comes from the XRAY lab and Raman Spectroscopy Lab, both focused on the development of advanced non-invasive XRay and Raman methods and their application to CH materials, and from the DHlab (Digital Heritage Innovation Lab) experienced in the design and development of interactive media applications.

FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS

FORTH – Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser (IESL), founded in 1983, is a leading research institute worldwide in lasers, photonics and materials science. In the context of Heritage Science (HS), IESL has pioneered the use of advanced laser technologies in diagnostics and conservation of monuments and art objects

Prompted by the need for on-site work, researchers at IESL have developed state-of-the-art mobile instrumentation for diagnostics and conservation that has been employed in several field campaigns at museums and archaeological sites in Greece, Europe and the Middle East. IESL has been operating as a European Research Infrastructure (RI) since 1990 and is among the founding members of LASERLAB EUROPE.

Figure 13: Homepage of the PERCEIVE website.

- From the Naples’ meeting display short videos and photos.
- Advertise the news about the project from each partner.
- Display conferences, meetings and scientific articles organised in Horizon Europe frame.
- Advertisement to Eurographic workshop, NTNU workshop.
- Communication campaigns.
- Activation of two e-mails: info@perceive-horizon.eu for everyone looking for more information on the project, and tech@perceive-horizon.eu specifically dedicated to experts looking for details on the technological aspects of the research.

2nd year website:

- Restyling of the website.
- Update the website with the section to present the related project (DCH CLUSTER 2)
- News per month about the project from each partner.
- Put short videos and photos of the PERCEIVE events.
- Communication campaigns.
- Display conferences, meetings and scientific articles organised in Horizon Europe frame.
- Gate to the Repo, Tools, Services and Prototypes, including manuals and tutorials.

3rd year portal:

- The Platform accessed through the website, will be the gate to the Repo, Tools, Services and Prototypes.
- One of the pages of the project website will contain an overview and archive of all published information: scientific articles, publications, press releases, etc.*
- Videos and examples of the prototypes applied to case studies.

3.7 Social Media Channels and plan

The Communication strategy will act at internal and external level providing a support tool for communication activities, to increase both coordination among the partners identifying a common language useful to achieve the expected results and high visibility to the project activities and outputs ensuring elevated level of accessibility and understanding to all targets. Internal communication focuses on ensuring a good collaboration system, defining punctual workflow and a reporting system among Partners. Partners must be aware of the purpose and their fundamental role in increasing the impact and visibility of the project.

A Google form was prepared, accessible for the partners, as the most appropriate instrument to facilitate the flow of information, simplifying the work and furthering relations and contributions of all the partners involved in the project implementation. Good internal communication management within the partnership is key for the successful external communication of the project. To invite partners to submit content for dissemination through social channels, a document was prepared with guidelines to follow. The document is available in **Annex 1**.

More details on internal communication can be reported in Deliverable 1.1 “Operational Plan, Progress Report, and Evaluation Report”.

External communication, on the other hand, aims at spreading project outputs and results throughout the included regions and to raise awareness in a wider audience of the included area. Main tool for external communication will be the official web platform.

The following social profiles were opened:

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/PERCEIVEhorizon>

Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/perceive_horizon/

Twitter: https://twitter.com/PERCEIVE_info

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/perceive-horizon/>

Telegram: Telegram channel “PERCEIVE” where we will send information and links of interest so that all partners are kept up to date with the activities taking place. The goal is then to broaden the audience beyond the partners involved in the project and make it a channel for communicating the possible technologies available for Cultural Heritage.

At the end of April 2024, we also launched the new **YouTube channel**, which will be regularly updated and whose content will be organised in playlists, with two formats already set up for behind-the-scenes videos and interviews with partners.

The Editorial Board decided to publish minimum **at least one post per week**, on the project channels:

1. Instagram, LinkedIn and Facebook: text with 1/2 images. The same text can be used for these three channels. In case the news is on the website insert the link;
2. X [ex Twitter]: short text with image, insert link with details.

Content to be shared weekly can be under one of the following categories:

- #PerceivePartner: post introducing the project partners, with link to the page on the Perceive website;
- #PerceiveScenarios: presentation of the 5 scenarios and case studies related to each scenario;
- #PerceivePublication: presentation of papers, popular and scientific that involved the project;
- #PerceiveOnTour: story about the acquisition campaigns done/to be done in partner museums.

Figure 14: Example of social media pages.

The first post was published on Tuesday, 4 April 2024 to present the project and the website. It was mostly published on Fridays in the following weeks, presenting the partners, working groups, and event participation.

To disseminate the content, a slideshow was created for the visual part, in video format on Instagram and Facebook, and pdf format on LinkedIn. Videos and photos have proven to be more engaging than purely text-based posts across nearly all internet platforms. On average, LinkedIn posts with images have a 98% higher comment rate, and tweets with visual content are three times more likely to get engagement. On Instagram, carousel posts have the highest engagement rate.

To make the content easily recognisable to followers, a colour palette was chosen that recalled those used in the project logo. A cover was created that made the content of the post immediately clear, visually appealing, and communicated the most information.

Particular attention was always taken to using hashtags and tagging the partners involved.

Here are some examples of posts shared on social channels:

INSTAGRAM

#PerceivePartner

Figure 15: Social media post example.

#PerceiveScenario

Scenario 3: Fading colors in Textiles

Figure 16: Social media post example.

FACEBOOK

#PerceiveOnTour

Cover

Image inside

Figure 17: Social media post example.

#PerceiveScenario #PerceivePartner

Cover

Image inside

Figure 18: Social media post example.

3.7 Newsletter

We launched in March 2024 the project's monthly newsletter, edited by early career researchers and postgraduate students, coordinated by the board, belonging to different partners' institutions (CNR, MUNCH, FORTH, Fraunhofer, NTNU).

The newsletter is organised in: a) Main article; b) "PERCEIVE recommend" section; c) "What's going on in PERCEIVE?" section; d) "Save the date" section. It currently counts 56 subscribers and is growing steadily, as is the percentage of unique openings and interactions of each campaign. Each month the newsletter includes insights, short articles and engaging materials on the different themes and topics of PERCEIVE to reach and connect with the project's audience.

March Newsletter: <https://mailchi.mp/4dc71de5e835/perceive-march-newsletter?e=5f1ae6b325>

April Newsletter: <https://mailchi.mp/c7598c0ec268/perceive-april-newsletter?e=5f1ae6b325>

Figure 19: March and April Newsletter

The newsletter is also shared on the project's social media channels and the most viewed content will also be featured on the homepage of the PERCEIVE website.

ANNEX 1

Guidelines of the Perceive Communication Plan

What to contact us for

In this document, we build a communication plan that will engage and inspire our audience. To make communication effective, we ask you to always update us about your initiatives/activities related to the project, to promote them and engage the public.

PROMOTION OF Perceive Project

through

- The PERCEIVE website
- PERCEIVE Social Channels: Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, Twitter
- YouTube channel

VISUAL IDENTITY

through

- Banners, flyers, postcards, posters for online and offline event connected with the project
- Creation of short promo videos to promote the activity of the project
- Video editing recorded exclusively by the Consortium (no third parties!)

How to contact us

E-MAIL

perceive-editorialboard@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

FORM ONLINE (for partners)

<https://forms.gle/6sabPd7X8wpbQSiD9>

MICROSOFT TEAMS

PERCEIVE communication

Index

1. Promoting Events & News / Publications
2. Issue a press release or press note
3. The YouTube channel
4. Editorial Calendar
5. Editorial Board Tools
1. Promoting Events & News / Publications

Contacts: perceive-editorialboard@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

- Are you organising a special session within a national / European / international conference?
- Would you like to tell about the activities carried out in the project?
- Do you want to promote Higher Education activities connected with the project?
- Do you want to promote your scientific publication connected with the project?

Procedure: The request should be made EXCLUSIVELY by filling in the online form for promotion requests. If necessary, you can contact the Editorial Board perceive-editorialboard@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

It is essential that the news be published FIRST on official project channels. Only later will it be possible to give it out through personal profiles. If the news has already been disseminated through other channels or web sites, the Editorial Board will consider whether to process the news for publication on PERCEIVE channels or to share from other sources only if they are reliable, giving preference to the channels of Institutional subjects.

Timing: send a request **2 weeks** before the news to be published, especially if it is an event where the organisers include the consortium or any of the partners.

Link to the form: <https://forms.gle/kDcJkgzTuWnNZKy47>

Issuing a press release or press note

Contacts: perceive-editorialboard@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

Procedure: Contact the reference person by email as soon as possible. It is always suggested to include the email address perceive-editorialboard@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com.

Send a brief abstract with the subject of the news, institutions involved, results achieved, possible impact in the specific field of scientific research, interest at the cultural, social and/or economic level.

It will be the Editorial Board's responsibility to verify whether the press release is the appropriate medium to promote the news. Once the content has been prepared, any other Press Offices of the institutions involved are contacted to coordinate the content of the release, dissemination channels and common timing of the launch.

If Editorial Board support is sought, remember that the same news item should not be sent, independently, to other press offices to avoid duplication.

Timing: Please send a request to the contact person 2 weeks before the news to be announced.

YouTube channels

Contacts: perceive-editorialboard@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

Procedure: Only videos that present the PERCEIVE graphics, that have been edited by the technical staff of the Editorial Board or made in collaboration with the staff charged by the Editorial Board, will be uploaded to the YouTube channel. In the case of video material that has these characteristics, or for suggestions, please send an email to ivana.cerato@cnr.it and

sofia.pescarin@cnr.it, always including the Editorial Board's address perceive-editorialboard@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com.

The material received will be viewed and, if it respects the policy, published on the project's YouTube channel. To allow for publication, please send along with each video a brief description of the content.

Editorial Calendar

During the first EB meeting, it was decided to publish at least one post per week, on the project channels:

1. Instagram, LinkedIn and Facebook: text with 1/2 images. The same text can be used for these three channels. In case the news is on the website insert the link;
2. Twitter: short text with image, insert link with details.

Content to be shared weekly can be under one of the following categories:

1. #PerceivePartner: post introducing the project partners, with link to the page on the Perceive website;
2. #PerceiveScenarios: presentation of the 5 scenarios and case studies related to each scenario;
3. #PerceivePublication: presentation of papers, popular and scientific that involved the project;
4. #PerceiveOnTheRoad: story about the acquisition campaigns done/to be done in partner museums.

It is preferably published on Mondays or Tuesdays, starting the first week of April.

All project partners will always be tagged in the posts. We always remind you to share from your personal and institutional profiles the posts.

Always follow the channels, these are the links:

- a. Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/PERCEIVEhorizon>
- b. Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/perceive_horizon/
- c. LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/perceive-horizon/>
- d. Twitter: https://twitter.com/PERCEIVE_info
- e. YouTube:

Editorial Board tools.

Editorial Board Requests Form

<https://forms.gle/vmeS6j3bzXr7QYtA9>

Official Logos & Fonts PERCEIVE

[Logo](#)

Hashtags for communication (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn)

#perceive, #perceivehorizon, #perceiveproject, #colorperceive, #perceiveNEWS,
#perceiveOnTour, #perceiveOnTheRoad, #perceiveEvent, #perceivePartner, #perceivecolors,
#perceivepainting, #perceivepolychromy, #perceivephotographs, #perceivetextiles,
#perceivedigitalart, #perceiveAI